

DIFFERENTIATION OF A FOUR-DIMENSIONAL NILPOTENT ALGEBRA

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ABSTRACT

Differentiation is one of the fundamental concepts of mathematics. Differentiations also play an important role in algebra. There are various generalizations of differentiations. These include antidifferentiations, δ -differentiations, ternary differentiations, and (α, β, γ) -differentiations. In this paper, the differentiation of four-dimensional nilpotent algebras is shown by proving local differentiation.

ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЦИЯ ЧЕТЫРЕХМЕРНОЙ НИЛЬПОТЕНТНОЙ АЛГЕБРЫ

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Дифференциация, алгебра, локальное дифференцирование, линейное отображение.

ABSTRACT

Дифференциация — одно из фундаментальных понятий математики. Дифференциации также играют важную роль в алгебре. Существуют различные обобщения дифференциаций. К ним относятся антидифференциации, δ -дифференциации, тернарные дифференциации и (α, β, γ) -дифференциации. В данной работе дифференциация четырехмерных нильпотентных алгебр демонстрируется путем доказательства локальной дифференциации.

TO'RT O'LCHAMLI NILPOTENT ALGEBRANING DIFFERENSIALLASHI

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KEYWORDS

Differensiallash, Algebra, lokal differensiallash, chiziqli akslatirish.

ABSTRACT

Differensiallash matematikaning fundamental tushunchalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Differensiallashlar algebra fanida ham muhim o‘rin tutadi. Differensiallashlarning turli umumlashmalari mavjud. Bular sarasiga antidifferensiallashlar, δ -differensiallashlar, ternar differensiallashlar va (α, β, γ) -differensiallashlar kiradi. Ushbu ishda to‘rt o‘lchamli nilpotent algebralarning differensiallashi isboti bilan ko‘rsatilgan.

Kirish

Quyida biz to‘rt o‘lchamli nilpotent algebralarning differensiallashini keltiramiz.

N_2 haqiqiy sonlar maydoni ustida aniqlangan $\{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4\}$ bazisli nilpotent algebra berilgan. Bu algebra ko‘paytirish jadvali quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$e_1e_1 = e_2 \quad e_2e_3 = e_4 \quad e_3e_2 = e_4 \quad e_3e_1 = e_4$$

N_2 algebra ixtiyoriy x vektorni

$$x = x_1e_1 + x_2e_2 + x_3e_3 + x_4e_4$$

ko‘rinishda yozish mumkin. $d : N_2 \rightarrow N_2$ akslantirishni qaraylik.

1-Ta’rif. Agar N algebra olingan ixtiyoriy x, y elementlar uchun

$$d(x \cdot y) = d(x) \cdot y + x \cdot d(y)$$

Tenglik bajarilsa d akslantirish qaralayotgan N algebra differensiallash deb ataladi.

$d(x) = Ax$ chiziqli akslantirishni qaraylik, bu yerda $A - 4 \times 4$ o‘lchamli kvadrat matritsa.

Ravshanki, agar N_2 algebra olingan ixtiyoriy x, y elementlar uchun

$$A(xy) = (Ax)y + x(Ay) \tag{1}$$

tenglik bajarilsa $d(x) = Ax$ akslantirish qaralayotgan N_2 algebra differensiallashdan iborat bo‘ladi.

1-Teorema. $d(x) = Ax$ akslantirish N_2 algebra differensiallashdan iborat bo‘lishi uchun A matritsa

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & a_{3,3} & 0 \\ a_{4,1} & 0 & a_{4,3} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} \tag{2}$$

ko‘rinishda bo‘lishi zarur va yetarli.

Isbot. Zarurligi. $d(x) = Ax$ akslantirish N_2 algebra differensiallashdan iborat bo‘sin. U holda

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} & a_{1,4} \\ a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} & a_{2,4} \\ a_{3,1} & a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} & a_{3,4} \\ a_{4,1} & a_{4,2} & a_{4,3} & a_{4,4} \end{pmatrix}$$

Matritsa ixtiyoriy x, y vektorlar uchun (1) tenglikni qanoatlantirishi kerak.

Xususan $e_1 e_1 = e_2$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_1)e_1 + e_1(Ae_1) = A(e_2)$$

qaraylik:

$$Ae_1 \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} & a_{1,4} \\ a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} & a_{2,4} \\ a_{3,1} & a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} & a_{3,4} \\ a_{4,1} & a_{4,2} & a_{4,3} & a_{4,4} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} \\ a_{2,1} \\ a_{3,1} \\ a_{4,1} \end{pmatrix} = a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{2,1}e_2 + a_{3,1}e_3 + a_{4,1}e_4$$

$$Ae_2 = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} & a_{1,4} \\ a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} & a_{2,4} \\ a_{3,1} & a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} & a_{3,4} \\ a_{4,1} & a_{4,2} & a_{4,3} & a_{4,4} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,2} \\ a_{2,2} \\ a_{3,2} \\ a_{4,2} \end{pmatrix} = a_{1,2}e_1 + a_{2,2}e_2 + a_{3,2}e_3 + a_{4,2}e_4$$

$$Ae_3 = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} & a_{1,4} \\ a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} & a_{2,4} \\ a_{3,1} & a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} & a_{3,4} \\ a_{4,1} & a_{4,2} & a_{4,3} & a_{4,4} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,3} \\ a_{2,3} \\ a_{3,3} \\ a_{4,3} \end{pmatrix} = a_{1,3}e_1 + a_{2,3}e_2 + a_{3,3}e_3 + a_{4,3}e_4$$

$$Ae_4 = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} & a_{1,4} \\ a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} & a_{2,4} \\ a_{3,1} & a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} & a_{3,4} \\ a_{4,1} & a_{4,2} & a_{4,3} & a_{4,4} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{1,4} \\ a_{2,4} \\ a_{3,4} \\ a_{4,4} \end{pmatrix} = a_{1,4}e_1 + a_{2,4}e_2 + a_{3,4}e_3 + a_{4,4}e_4$$

$$(Ae_1)e_1 = (a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{2,1}e_2 + a_{3,1}e_3 + a_{4,1}e_4)e_1 = a_{1,1}e_2 + a_{3,1}e_4$$

$$e_1(Ae_1) = e_1(a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{2,1}e_2 + a_{3,1}e_3 + a_{4,1}e_4) = a_{1,1}e_2$$

$$a_{1,1}e_2 + a_{3,1}e_4 + a_{1,1}e_2 = a_{1,2}e_1 + a_{2,2}e_2 + a_{3,2}e_3 + a_{4,2}e_4$$

bundan

$$a_{2,2} = 2a_{1,1}, \quad a_{1,2} = 0, \quad a_{3,2} = 0 \quad a_{4,2} = a_{3,1} \quad Ae_2 = 2a_{1,1}e_2 + a_{3,1}e_4$$

tengliklarni aniqlaymiz.

Endi $e_1 e_2 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_1)e_2 + e_1(Ae_2) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$(Ae_1)e_2 = (a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{2,1}e_2 + a_{3,1}e_3 + a_{4,1}e_4)e_2 = a_{3,1}e_4$$

$$e_1(Ae_2) = e_1(2a_{1,1}e_2 + a_{3,1}e_4) = 0$$

$$a_{3,1}e_4 = 0$$

bundan

$$a_{3,1} = 0, \quad a_{4,2} = 0 \quad Ae_2 = 2a_{1,1}e_2 \quad Ae_1 = a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{2,1}e_2 + a_{4,1}e_4$$

tengliklarni aniqlaymiz.

Endi $e_1 e_3 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_1)e_3 + e_1(Ae_3) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$(Ae_1)e_3 = (a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{2,1}e_2 + a_{4,1}e_4)e_3 = a_{2,1}e_4$$

$$e_1(Ae_3) = e_1(a_{1,3}e_1 + a_{2,3}e_2 + a_{3,3}e_3 + a_{4,3}e_4) = a_{1,3}e_2$$

$$a_{2,1}e_4 + a_{1,3}e_2 = 0$$

bundan

$$a_{1,3} = 0, \quad a_{2,1} = 0 \quad Ae_1 = a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{4,1}e_4 \quad Ae_3 = a_{2,3}e_2 + a_{3,3}e_3 + a_{4,3}e_4$$

tengliklarni aniqlaymiz.

Endi $e_1e_4 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_1)e_4 + e_1(Ae_4) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$\begin{aligned}(Ae_1)e_4 &= (a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{4,1}e_4)e_4 = 0 \\ e_1(Ae_4) &= e_1(a_{1,4}e_1 + a_{2,4}e_2 + a_{3,4}e_3 + a_{4,4}e_4) = a_{1,4}e_2 \\ a_{1,4}e_2 &= 0\end{aligned}$$

bundan

$$a_{1,4} = 0, \quad Ae_4 = a_{2,4}e_2 + a_{3,4}e_3 + a_{4,4}e_4$$

tengliklarni aniqlaymiz.

Endi $e_2e_1 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_2)e_1 + e_2(Ae_1) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$\begin{aligned}(Ae_2)e_1 &= (2a_{1,1}e_2)e_1 = 0 \\ e_2(Ae_1) &= e_2(a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{4,1}e_4) = 0 \\ 0 &= 0\end{aligned}$$

bo'ldi.

Endi $e_2e_2 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_2)e_2 + e_2(Ae_2) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$\begin{aligned}(Ae_2)e_2 &= (2a_{1,1}e_2)e_2 = 0 \\ e_2(Ae_2) &= e_2(2a_{1,1}e_2) = 0 \\ 0 &= 0\end{aligned}$$

bo'ldi.

Endi $e_2e_3 = e_4$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_2)e_3 + e_2(Ae_3) = A(e_4)$$

qaraylik:

$$\begin{aligned}(Ae_2)e_3 &= (2a_{1,1}e_2)e_3 = 2a_{1,1}e_4 \\ e_2(Ae_3) &= e_2(a_{2,3}e_2 + a_{3,3}e_3 + a_{4,3}e_4) = a_{3,3}e_4 \\ 2a_{1,1}e_4 + a_{3,3}e_4 &= a_{2,4}e_2 + a_{3,4}e_3 + a_{4,4}e_4\end{aligned}$$

bundan

$$a_{2,4} = 0, \quad a_{3,4} = 0, \quad a_{4,4} = 2a_{1,1} + a_{3,3} \quad Ae_4 = (2a_{1,1} + a_{3,3})e_4$$

tengliklarni aniqlaymiz.

Endi $e_2e_4 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_2)e_4 + e_2(Ae_4) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$\begin{aligned}(Ae_2)e_4 &= (2a_{1,1}e_2)e_4 = 0 \\ e_2(Ae_4) &= e_2(2a_{1,1} + a_{3,3})e_4 = 0 \\ 0 &= 0\end{aligned}$$

bo'ldi.

Endi $e_3e_1 = e_4$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_3)e_1 + e_3(Ae_1) = A(e_4)$$

qaraylik:

$$(Ae_3)e_1 = (a_{2,3}e_2 + a_{3,3}e_3 + a_{4,3}e_4)e_1 = a_{3,3}e_4$$

$$e_3(Ae_1) = e_3(a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{4,1}e_4) = a_{1,1}e_4$$

$$a_{3,3}e_4 + a_{1,1}e_4 = (2a_{1,1} + a_{3,3})e_4$$

$$a_{3,3} + a_{1,1} = 2a_{1,1} + a_{3,3}$$

bundan

$$a_{1,1} = 0, \quad Ae_1 = a_{4,1}e_4 \quad Ae_2 = 0 \quad Ae_4 = a_{3,3}e_4$$

tengliklarni aniqlaymiz.

Endi $e_3e_2 = e_4$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_3)e_2 + e_3(Ae_2) = A(e_4)$$

qaraylik:

$$(Ae_3)e_2 = (a_{2,3}e_2 + a_{3,3}e_3 + a_{4,3}e_4)e_2 = a_{3,3}e_4,$$

$$e_3(Ae_2) = e_3(0) = 0$$

$$a_{3,3}e_4 = a_{3,3}e_4$$

$$0 = 0$$

bo'ldi.

Endi $e_3e_3 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_3)e_3 + e_3(Ae_3) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$(Ae_3)e_3 = (a_{2,3}e_2 + a_{3,3}e_3 + a_{4,3}e_4)e_3 = a_{2,3}e_4$$

$$e_3(Ae_3) = e_3(a_{2,3}e_2 + a_{3,3}e_3 + a_{4,3}e_4) = a_{2,3}e_4$$

$$a_{2,3} + a_{2,3} = 0$$

bundan

$$a_{2,3} = 0 \quad Ae_3 = a_{3,3}e_3 + a_{4,3}e_4$$

tengliklarni aniqlaymiz

Endi $e_3e_4 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_3)e_4 + e_3(Ae_4) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$(Ae_3)e_4 = (a_{3,3}e_3 + a_{4,3}e_4)e_4 = 0,$$

$$e_3(Ae_4) = e_3(a_{3,3}e_4) = 0$$

$$0 = 0$$

bo'ldi.

Endi $e_4e_1 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_4)e_1 + e_4(Ae_1) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$(Ae_4)e_1 = (a_{3,3}e_4)e_1 = 0,$$

$$e_4(Ae_1) = e_4(a_{4,1}e_4) = 0$$

$$0 = 0$$

bo'ldi.

Endi $e_4e_2 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_4)e_2 + e_4(Ae_2) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$(Ae_4)e_2 = (a_{3,3}e_4)e_2 = 0, \quad e_4(Ae_2) = e_4(0) = 0 \\ 0 = 0$$

bo'ldi.

Endi $e_4e_3 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_4)e_3 + e_4(Ae_3) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$(Ae_4)e_3 = (a_{3,3}e_4)e_3 = 0, \quad e_4(Ae_3) = e_4(a_{3,3}e_3 + a_{4,3}e_4) = 0 \\ 0 = 0$$

bo'ldi.

Endi $e_4e_4 = 0$ tenglikdan foydalanib quyidagi ayniyatni

$$(Ae_4)e_4 + e_4(Ae_4) = A(0)$$

qaraylik:

$$(Ae_4)e_4 = (a_{3,3}e_4)e_4 = 0, \quad e_4(Ae_4) = e_4(a_{3,3}e_4) = 0 \\ 0 = 0$$

bo'ldi.

Yetarliligi. Endi A matritsa (2) ko'rinishda bo'lsa $d(x) = Ax$ chiziqli akslantirish differensiallashdan iboratligini ko'rsataylik.

$$xy = (x_1e_1 + x_2e_2 + x_3e_3 + x_4e_4)(y_1e_1 + y_2e_2 + y_3e_3 + y_4e_4) = \\ = x_1y_1e_2 + (x_2y_3 + x_3y_1 + x_3y_2)e_4$$

Tenglikka ko'ra

$$A(xy) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & a_{3,3} & 0 \\ a_{4,1} & 0 & a_{4,3} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ x_1y_1 \\ 0 \\ x_2y_3 + x_3y_1 + x_3y_2 \end{pmatrix} = \\ = a_{3,3}x_2y_3 + a_{3,3}x_3y_1 + a_{3,3}x_3y_2$$

boshqa tamondan

$$Ax = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & a_{3,3} & 0 \\ a_{4,1} & 0 & a_{4,3} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \\ x_4 \end{pmatrix} = \\ = a_{3,3}x_3e_3 + (a_{4,1}x_1 + a_{4,3}x_3 + a_{3,3}x_4)e_4$$

$$(Ax)y = (a_{3,3}x_3e_3 + (a_{4,1}x_1 + a_{4,3}x_3 + a_{3,3}x_4)e_4)(y_1e_1 + y_2e_2 + y_3e_3 + y_4e_4) = \\ = a_{3,3}x_3y_1e_4 + a_{3,3}x_3y_2e_4$$

$$Ay = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & a_{3,3} & 0 \\ a_{4,1} & 0 & a_{4,3} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \\ y_4 \end{pmatrix} = \\ = a_{3,3}y_3e_3 + (a_{4,1}y_1 + a_{4,3}y_3 + a_{3,3}y_4)e_4$$

$$x(Ay) = (x_1e_1 + x_2e_2 + x_3e_3 + x_4e_4)(a_{3,3}y_3e_3 + (a_{4,1}y_1 + a_{4,3}y_3 + a_{3,3}y_4)e_4) = \\ = a_{3,3}x_2y_3e_4$$

Yuqoridagi xisoblashlar (2) tenglik to'g'riligini ko'rsatadi. **Teorema isbotlandi.**

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